

Testing a yield loss simulation model for rice in Chinese rice-wheat system production environments

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A yield loss simulation model for rice pests was developed (Willocquet et al 1998, 2000) as a tool for setting research priorities and improving pest management. This model is production situation (PS)-specific and addresses yield loss caused by several rice pests. The model has been tested in several PSs in the Philippines, Vietnam, and northern India, using field experiments done at different sites. In most cases, the model adequately simulated the attainable growth of a rice crop, as well as losses from various pests (diseases, insects, and weeds) (Willocquet et al 1998, 1999a,b, 2000). The work reported here was aimed at further testing this model under PSs and injuries prevailing in the Chinese rice-wheat system. The PSs and injuries addressed here were defined based on the characterization of rice injury profiles and PSs recently done across tropical Asia (Savary et al 2000). The first PS, PS2, is a reference used in all field-test experiments. Two other PSs (PS6 and PS7) represent PSs prevailing in Zhejiang Province. Whiteheads caused by stem borers, sheath blight, and weeds are considered as common rice pests in the province.

An experiment was done at CNRRI during the 1998 rainy season using “early rice.” Crop establishment in the field was done on 27 April. In each PS, injury-free plots and rice plots injured by pests (alone or in combination) were established. Crop growth, environmental factors, and pest injuries were monitored throughout the growing season. In a given PS, data from injury-free plots were used to calibrate parameters to simulate attainable yield. Data from injured plots were used to test simulations of yield losses.

Three PSs were addressed: PS2 (IR72 transplanted with young seedlings,

110 kg N ha⁻¹, irrigated rice), PS6 (Jian Yu 293, direct-seeded at a density of 170 germinated seeds m⁻², 180 kg N ha⁻¹ in three splits, 15 kg P ha⁻¹ at basal, 75 kg K ha⁻¹ in two splits), and PS7 (Fan 97 transplanted with 28-d-old seedlings, 100 kg N ha⁻¹ in seedbed, same fertilization as PS6). Three injury treatments were established in each PS: whiteheads (WH), sheath blight (ShB), weeds (WEED), a combination of the three injuries (COMBI), and a noninjured (CTRL) treatment. The injury treatments were randomized with three replications in each PS. Individual plots were 2.8 × 2.8 m and included four zones from the outer to the inner part of the plot: a border row, 20 cm wide; a sampling zone, 20 cm wide, to monitor crop growth (destructive sam-

plings) and injuries; a second row, 20 cm wide; and a central harvest area.

The simulations of attainable growth (leaf, stem, root, and panicle dry weight, and tiller population) and final yield were close to observed values (see figure) in the three PSs considered. In all PSs, the same patterns were observed: increase in leaf weight until flowering, then a decline (leaf senescence); increase in root weight until flowering, remaining stable afterward; increase in stem weight until flowering, then a decline (translocation of stored starch from the stems to the panicles); and an increase in panicle weight from flowering to maturity. Tillering occurred until 30–40 d after crop establishment (DACE). The number of

Attainable rice growth in three PSs (A: PS2, B: PS6, C: PS7): observed (dots) ± SEM and simulated (plain line) dry weight (g m⁻²) of roots (ROOTW), dry weight of leaves (LEAFW), dry weight of stems (STEMW), dry weight of panicles (PANW), and number (m⁻²) of tillers (TOTIL). Observed data were collected from the experiment done at CNRRI in 1998 in control plots (see text for details).

tillers declined afterward because of tiller death and remained constant after flowering. The crop cycle was shorter in PS6 and PS7 than in PS2. The maximum leaf dry weight and the maximum number of tillers were much smaller in PS7 than in PS2 and PS6. This is probably because of the crop establishment method in PS7 (using old transplanted seedlings), which favored the growth of a small number of big tillers. The maximum dry weight of stems was observed in PS2 and was attributed to the longer crop cycle in this PS, which allowed the stem to grow for a long time. The final yield was largest in PS7, followed by PS6 and PS2. The lower fertilization in PS2 than in the two other PSs explains the poorer performance of this PS.

The table gives simulated and observed grain yields for the 15 (PS × injury) combinations addressed in the experiment. Yield loss ranged from 0.3% to 24%. An acceptance interval of ± 10% of the observed grain yield was defined to assess simulated yield outputs. The model simulated yields within this acceptance interval in all cases. It can thus be assumed that the model accounted well for the effects of different injuries manipulated in this experiment.

Results show that the simulation model adequately describes PSs and re-

Simulated and observed grain yield (g m⁻²) in the experiment done at CNRRI in 1998.

Treatment ^a	PS2 ^b		PS6 ^b		PS7 ^b	
	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated
CTRL	422	418	579	568	787	787
WH	420	408	-	-	-	-
SHB	393	402	519	517	689	711
WEED	319	331	523	550	669	686
COMBI	361	343	509	493	611	670

^aCTRL = control, WH = white heads, SHB = sheath blight, WEED = weeds, COMBI = combination of the three injuries.

^bPS2 = reference production situation, PS6 and PS7 = production situations that prevail in Zhejiang Province.

flects fairly well the damage caused by sheath blight, weeds, and whiteheads, alone or in combination. Previous evaluations of the model yielded similar conclusions under different sets of PSs (Willoquet et al 1998, 1999a,b, 2000). This study shows that the model behaves fairly well under other rice production environments, such as those found in Zhejiang Province.

The simple model structure and the approach used to calibrate and test it can be used by different research teams to address specific (PS × injuries) combinations. The model is flexible enough to address other injuries, such as those caused by brown planthopper, bacterial leaf blight, or defoliators. It can thus be used for scenario analyses that may help in prioritizing research for rice pest management.

References

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Analysis of spatial structure and distribution of brown planthopper at a macro-scale level

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Brown planthopper (BPH) is a migrant insect pest and is observed to complete about seven to eight generations in Guangdong Province of China (Bao et al 1996). Its spatial structure and distribution are complex and difficult to predict at a macro-scale level. Early studies tried to

describe distribution using classical statistics, neglecting the spatial location of samples and their interdependence. To capture these spatial relations, we have adapted a geostatistical modeling approach to predict the density distribution of BPH.

In this study, BPH density was considered as a typical regionalized variable, and the semivariogram—a function describing the relationship between distance and sample values—was used as a tool to analyze its spatial structure (Journel 1984). The Kriging interpolation technique,